

REPORT: BioMedBridges standards workshop

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1 Introduction

This workshop, co-organized by BioMedBridges WP3 and 12, was held on 24-25 June and hosted by BioMedBridges partners at VUMC in Amsterdam. Attendees included BioMedBridges personnel, members from the ESFRI BMS research infrastructures and invited external experts from existing standards organisations.

The following aspects of data standardisation were explored:

- Defining entity identifiers and identifiers best practice
- Development of a Meta models and Mappings Registry for biomedical standards

Data integration occurs when a query proceeds through multiple data sets, thereby relating diverse data extracted from different data sources. Standards and data harmonisation is a prerequisite to data integration, a primary aim of the BioMedBridges project. For the various ESFRI projects to exchange and integrate data in a meaningful way there needs to be agreement on how biomedical data is annotated, formatted and organised. Whilst an ultimate aim would be a single database, with a standardised user interface (UI), this is unlikely and a system of federated databases each specialising in a particular data type is more achievable. Provided that standardisation is implemented across the databases, a common UI could be deployed to allow integrated and simultaneous searching of data.

The use of entity identifiers and common standards is essential to achieve the above vision, but many challenges exist. The complex and varied nature of the biomedical sciences, and biology in general, means that each researcher can have their own requirements and reasons for structuring their data in a particular format. To capture the possible extent of these variables, standards would require a high degree of granularity. Therefore organisation is required within the community and compromise needs to be sought.

2 Identifiers

Our current biological knowledge is spread over many independent datasets and bioinformatics databases where many different types of terminology are used. One difficulty this creates is the reliable identification of data entities where resources may re-purpose data or provide alternative avenues for accessing it. This can cause problems when attempting to locate original data and avoid redundant analysis. The use of community accepted identifiers that have been denoted by a central authority can simplify this process and better provide unambiguous information about data entities. The provision and use of common identifiers is key to supporting the information flow from basic science, model organism biology, bioinformatics and structural biology through to translational research and clinical care.

In preparation for the workshop, WP3 asked partners from all ESFRI BMS to review the current scientific entities and matching standards. In addition, partners were asked to contribute to a gap analysis of standards and identifiers by flagging areas where no identifier standard exists or where tooling for ID mapping and conversion is lacking. The results of these activities were fed into the workshop and formed the basis of breakout sessions of the themes below:

1. Identifier management & formats
2. Identifier resolution
3. Identifier usage - mapping / aggregation
4. Identifier cataloguing
5. Identifier gap analysis

One area that was highlighted in both the gap analysis and the discussion sessions was the lack of standards in the area of biological and clinical imaging. Participants considered ways in which this gap could be closed by future standards development, noted as being a difficult challenge but important to the work of several ESFRI BMS (notably Euro-BioImaging & INFRAFRONTIER).

The outcomes from the day on identifiers contributed towards meeting the recommendations from the BioMedBridges Scientific Advisory Board, which had

called for greater cooperation between the project and other EU initiatives working in this area. Future workshops will bring the participants together again to discuss this area further.

Following the meeting WP3 Standards produced a document outlining best practices in creating, managing and using identifiers¹, which describes recommendations for best practice in the design and use of identifiers as part of the BioMedBridges project. It covers identifier assignment, resolution, mapping and provenance, based on community scenarios from the Biomedical and Science research infrastructures partnered in BioMedBridges. Currently the guidelines are limited in scope to the biomedical field, but could be extended to other areas if needed.

3 Registries

The workshop provided an opportunity to discuss key standards for inclusion in registries, the commonalities between various standard organisations and existing registries, and focus areas for future collaboration. A series of invited speakers allowed participants to gain a wider understanding of the standards landscape in the areas of biomedical data, microbiology, metabolomics and clinical trials within and outside of BioMedBridges.

3.1 Meta models and Mappings Registry

The BioMedBridges Meta models and Mappings Registry² (deliverable 3.2) under development aims to facilitate syntactic operability across research infrastructures so that samples and data can be integrated and analysed across biomedical science domains. The current development plans of the registry³, which aims to address specific user needs in the biobanking community, were presented.

¹ [Best practices in creating, managing and using identifiers](#)

² <https://molgenis08.target.rug.nl/>

³ http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/3_-_morris_swertz_standards_registry_overview.pdf

Workshop participants discussed practical usage of the Meta models and Mappings Registry, exploring user perspectives on locating, comparing and selecting standards to use with particular datasets. The user interface was identified as an important topic for future discussion, and it was noted that end-users should be considered early on during the development⁴.

3.2 Identifiers.org

Identifiers.org⁵ provides URI-based resolvable identifiers for life science data. The presentation⁶ highlighted simple provisioning for RDF integration available within the URIs and the growing need for wider community awareness and support of identifier use.

3.3 BioSharing

BioSharing presented^{7,8} their registries and extensive work in mapping the landscape of community standards, databases, data policies and the interrelations between them. Started as the MIBBI Portal to register minimum information checklists, BioSharing now includes this and has been extended to terminologies (working with BioPortal) and formats (over 500 registered and curated standards). BioSharing is also part of the ELIXIR-UK Node and of two NIH BD2K centres: CEDAR⁹ and BioCADDIE¹⁰. The BioSharing community (and Board) operates the RDA BioSharing Working Group¹¹.

⁴ see also BioMedBridges WP2 user-centred design deliverable
<http://www.biomedbridges.eu/deliverables/23>

⁵ <http://identifiers.org>

⁶ [http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/5 - nick_juty - identifiers.org_.pdf](http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/5_-_nick_juty_-_identifiers.org_.pdf)

⁷ <http://biosharing.org/>

⁸ [BioSharing presentation on SlideShare](#)

⁹ <http://metadata.org>

¹⁰ <http://biocaddie.org/>

¹¹ [RDA BioSharing working group](#)

4 Standards groups

4.1 Clinical research: CDISC

CDISC presented on their global work with volunteers to develop data standards for clinical research. Whilst the work is predominantly focused on US clinical research and pharmaceutical development, it was acknowledged that work could be done to improve the academic gaps in the standards overseen by CDISC.

4.2 Biobank information: BioShare

Bioshare presented BiobankConnect¹², a project that aims to pool and harmonise datasets from multiple biobanks to increase the power of statistical analyses, for example in identifying disease risks of individual patients.

4.3 Microbial resources: MIRRI

MIRRI presented¹³ standardisation strategies to facilitate access to high-quality microorganisms and associated data for research, development and application.

4.4 Systems biology: ISBE

ISBE presented¹⁴ on the need for industry, academia and clinicians to adopt standards in systems biology. ISBE are interacting with multiple aspects of biology and wish to collaborate for better standard adoption by the community.

¹² http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/9_-_bioshare_-_chao_pang.pdf

¹³ http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/7_-_anna_klindworth_-_mirri.pdf

¹⁴ http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/8_-_katy_wolstencroft_-_isbe.pdf

4.5 Microbiology and environmental research: GSC

GSC presented¹⁵ work on the development of standards for genomic, metagenomic and genetics markers. These are essential as the full potential of sequence analysis data in microbiology and environmental research can only be realised in the respective geographic and environmental context (“contextual data”).

4.6 Coordination between resources

To avoid duplication of efforts and content, participants identified the following existing registries and resources for possible cross-referencing and integration:

- BioSharing
- identifiers.org
- EDAM¹⁶
- Tools and Data Services Registry¹⁷

Collaboration between these resources was highlighted as an important step in serving those seeking information, identifying areas where duplication or gaps in coverage exist, and to promote harmonization¹⁸.

5 Outcomes

- The standards landscape beyond biomedical data was explored, including microbiology, metabolomics, imaging and clinical trials...
- A review of the state-of-the-art across these disciplines identified key standards and current gaps in provision
- Areas of collaboration at basic levels identified include:

¹⁵ http://www.biomedbridges.eu/sites/biomedbridges.eu/files/training/6_-_pelin_yilmaz_-_gsc_mixs_gfbio.pdf

¹⁶ <http://biportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/EDAM?p=classes>

¹⁷ <http://bioregistry.cbs.dtu.dk>

¹⁸ A follow-up workshop was held at EMBL-EBI in Hinxton on 1 October 2014: <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-resource-integration>

- Linking resources and expertise
 - Training for data developers and end-users
 - Awareness of standards
- Participants reached an understanding of common challenges faced in the field and agreed to look at developing collaborative solutions to these challenges

6 Actions from the workshop

- Write a document on “best practice for identifiers”
- Develop use cases to explore identifier application
- Write a paper on identifier best practice
- Organise a discussion on interactions with identifiers.org, biosharing.org, Tools and Data Services Registry and the EDAM ontology¹
- Address need for a common API across the standards resources

Appendix 1: List of attendees

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